

ISSN: 2582-7561

International Journal For Academic Research & Development

Vol. 3 (2021)

Issue 3

(Multidisciplinary)

E-mail Id: editor@iifard.org

url: www.iifard.org/about-journal/

www.iifard.org

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL FOR ACADEMIC RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL FOR ACADEMIC RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT

<https://iifard.org/web/AWABbgJhBD0=/IJARD>

www.iifard.org

ISSN: 2582-7561

I J A R D

Editor in Chief

Prof.(Dr.) Mohit Saxena

Editorial Board

Prof.(Dr.) Michael Gr. Voskoglou

Prof.(Dr.) Dimitrios A. Karras

Prof.(Dr.) Xiao-Zhi Gao

Prof.(Dr.) Akhtem A. Dzhelilov

Prof.(Dr.) Francesca Di Virgilio

Dr. Entessar Al Jbawi

Dr. Haiam Morsy Aboul-Ela

Prof.(Dr.) Khalil KASSMI

Dr. Osuji Emeka Emmanuel

Dr. Mateus Gianni Fonseca

**Volume 3, Issue 3
2021**

Published by

International Institute For Academic Research and Development

Email: trustforacademic@gmail.com, editor@iifard.org

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL FOR ACADEMIC RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL FOR ACADEMIC RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT

<https://iifard.org/web/AWABbgJhBD0=/IJARD>

www.iifard.org

ISSN: 2582-7561

About Journal - I J A R D

International Journal for Academic, Research and Development (IJARD) is an autonomous, peer reviewed online journal. It mainly serves as universal discussion identified with building training, distributed at present quarterly. IJARD welcomes researchers and academicians to submit their original research work which meets the journal criteria of significance and scientific excellence. IJARD is scholarly online open access and peer received journals emphasizing on research studies and application in the field of Science, Engineering and Management. Researchers are requested to submit their original articles online for a peer review and analysis before its publication. The editorial board encourages academicians, research scholars and partitions to publish their articles related to science, engineering and management and relevant fields.

IJARD publishes its journals in full open access format. The scientific community and the general public can unlimitedly and immediately access all content published in our journals for free as soon as it is published on the Internet. Therefore, IJARD needs to defray its editorial and production costs by collecting article processing charges from authors' institutes for research funding bodies. IJARD is committed to keep its open access publication charges at a minimum level.

We believe that immediate, worldwide, barrier-free, open access to the full text of research articles is in the best interests of the scientific community. We also intend to build mutually beneficial and long-lasting relationships with our authors and always provide them full support throughout the publishing and the post-publishing processes.

IJARD invites contribution in the following categories:

Original research work.

Review articles, comprehensive review on a topic.

Survey on a topic

Self-contained articles on ongoing research.

Technical Notes.

IJARD is committed to publishing only original work including research which has neither been published elsewhere, nor is under review elsewhere. All manuscripts that are found to have been plagiarized from a manuscript by other authors, whether published or unpublished, will incur plagiarism sanctions. Conference papers are very welcome; however it is imperative that these papers are significantly revised and updated. Actually, such papers have a better chance of acceptance if their merits were already prescreened at high quality conferences.

Manuscript should be submitted at <https://iifard.org/web/AmMJZIY1V24=/IJARD>

All correspondence should be made to editor@iifard.org trustforacademic@gmail.com

Phone no./WhatsApp: +918005351780, +67571280255

Welcome to International Journal for Academic, Research and Development !!!

www.iifard.org

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL FOR ACADEMIC RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL FOR ACADEMIC RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT

<https://iifard.org/web/AWABbgJhBD0=/IJARD>

www.iifard.org

ISSN: 2582-7561

Indexed with

ADVANCED SCIENCE INDEX

ASOS
indeks

ISSN

INTERNATIONAL
STANDARD
SERIAL
NUMBER

INTERNATIONAL CENTRE

Employee retention has become difficult due to workplace annoyances

Pal Jyotsana

NIMT, India

jyotsnapal13@gmail.com

Abstract

Every worker simply wants to be empowered to do a good job and be recognized for their contribution. If the CEO does not clearly communicate how employees can contribute to organizational goal and provide adequate training and performance feedback. They risk losing their best people as the economies improves this kind of labor turnover is costly and can also reduce company's competitive edge. Nothing affect employee's morale insidiously than persistent workplace negativity. It SAP's the energy of your organization and diverts critical attention from work and performance. Negativity occur in the attitude outlook and talk of one department member or in a crescendo of voices responding to a workplace decision or events

1. Introduction

There are five Reasons for Negativity

- 1.1 An excessive workload.
- 1.2 An excessive concern about management "s ability to lead the company forward successfully
- 1.3 Anxiety about the future, particular longer term job, income and retirement security.
- 1.4 Lack of challenge in their work with boredom intensifying existing frustration about workload.
- 1.5 Insufficient recognition for the level of contribution and effort provided and concern that there pay isn't commensurate with performance

An Employees who applies for a promotional opportunity, and does not get the job can be extremely negative, especially if promotional opportunity are perceived as limited you must take great care to make sure your promotion system is fair and that employees known exactly what they need to do to get ready for the next opportunity.

Employees love recognition : For their work they also like to see salary increase for contributing employees , One of the most cause of the employees negativity occurs when employees believes poor contributors received raises especially when their own raises was below their expectation. Employees are concerned about both management and their future with the company .Insecure employees are negative and looking for the worst to happen. Following a period of financial cases management has to work hard to regain employees trust.

2. Reasons for their negativity:

2.1 The employees has too much to do, too much of the time:

When the employees are overburdened with task , projects and other responsibilities for longer period of time , they may become resentful , fatigued and may feel stressed , all of this may lead to increased error , deteriorating relationship and job dissatisfaction while these people previously may have functioned as A and B players . They now have slipped in status due to chronic over work.

2.2 The employees is not well matched for the Job:

When staff aren't appropriately matched to a particular position they don't perform to their maximum potential , further the work doesn't get done the way it need to be done . Mismatch can mean lack of skill lack of interest lack of insight lack of maturity this result when it is not well matched with the job.

2.3 The Employees Dislike Boss:

This is very true that it is possible to dislike the boss, but still have to get the job done right. Lots of folks don't especially like their boss When the feeling become extreme, However the situation usually gets out of hand .Staff may reduce productivity, communicate poorly and in general make life miserable for those around them which effect the organization, as a result it may loose good employees of the organization and may also act as a hurdle for efficient employees from joining the organization.

2.4 The Employees Constantly Bring Problems From Home Into The Work Place:

Most human being are dealing with at least one problem in their personal life at any given time. Such problem include marital challenges , parenting issues , illness , financial struggles and external family difficulties people who use these problems include marital challenges parenting issues illness financial struggles and extended family difficulties regularly as handy excuses for unacceptable behavior breaches in policy and low productivity become "Problem Employee" Such employee creates problem for himself as well as become problem for others and through his behavior make other employees irritated.

2.5 The Employees Receive Poor Supervision:

Employees who are not getting proper supervision from their bosses eventually may turn into problem staffers. Their frustration is over not having a credible leader ,a dependable resource a candidate provider of feedback and /or a confidential sounding board can cause them to resort to inappropriate displays of anger deliberate choices to accomplish less than expected and conscious

decision to undermine the boss whenever possible as they are mentally stressed and frustrated as a result they are unable to concentrate on their work , which in turn result low productivity.

2.6 The Employees Is Unclear About The Big Picture:

Most Employees want to know how the individual job duties fit into the large company vision. Understanding this important process actually motivates people to do their best it gives meaning to everything they do When people are unclear about this .They may become complacent disinterested , even hostile their lack of motivation whether or not discussed with peers seeps like a poison throughout the department .

2.7 The Employees has the personality disorder:

The employee's expectation don't align with the company's or boss's expectation .When major misalignment is evident employees become problem. Employees have to feel some alignment in order to perform well, interact with other affectively and remain motivated .Serious misalignment usually leads to employees departure either voluntary or involuntary .If you question this think about spouses who don't agree about the significant goal of the marriage and direction for their future together .The marriage is likely to end at some point .Same is the case with the employees misalignment.

2.8 The Employees Is Basically Immature:

The degree to which employees are mature typically determines the amount of success they experience at work .Immature employees think its "ok" to break rules, gossip in ways that injures others, ask for special treatment, question authority at every turn and behave inappropriately on a daily bases immature employees risk not being promoted or recommended for additional responsibilities they also risk taking employed with their current company.

2.9 The Employees Find That The Job Reality Doesn't Fulfill His Fantasy :

A real problem develops when an employee's discover that the current job isn't the dream job, while this realization is a big disappointment. It can lead to something more threatening than an awareness of feeling associated with loss .It can demotivate someone to the point where he/she fails to produce to be a team player, fails to follow regulation, protocol of the organization. High employees' turnover and retention of skilled employees continued to be major problem s for employers last year.

Sales marketing , customers services and support staff were the most difficult employees to retain in most of the companies are using monetary related method to retain pronto line employees where turnover is the highest for examples using better compensation and benefits tut ion reimbursement, profits sharing and providing health insurance where as some are using non-

monetary method to retain employees at all level , including front line employees , middle managers , senior level executives non-monetary method include casual – dress codes , flexible hours and schedule in addition company are conducting interview more often providing mentoring program and have improved their orientation and training program.

3. Even good managers frustrate their employees now and then the most common things they do without realizing it are as follows

3.1 Making Social Events Unofficially Required:

Employers frequently assume that employees will view social events (like holidays hours, party) as a treat and then get offended when employees don't want to go. Most employees would prefer that Employers make it clear that when events are mandatory rather than implying they're optional and then penalizing people who don't attend. Requiring employees to attend events that are ostensibly to build morale may have the opposite effect.

3.2 Pressuring Employees To Donate To Charity :

Employers often mean well when they organize work place charity drive but too often manager's pressure employees to donate and even monitor individual participation. Charity drive are great but participation need to be strictly voluntary. How employees spent their money is their business not their employers

3.3 Calling Employees Who Are On Vocation :

Too many employers act as if employees are on call Day and Night .Even when they are on vocation. When they are interrupted by calls and email from office .Companies that operates this may annoy employees and have trouble in retaining them.

3.4 Holding Endless Meeting :

When employees are forces to sit in a long and endless meeting .But it's also incredibly common .Most employees report that they waste their too many hours a week in meeting without clear agenda or purpose and are forced to sit and listen their idle conversation when they would be working productively at their desk.

3.5 Not Making Hard Decision:

One common way this plays out is with managers who won't address performance problems or fire under performers and if you have ever worked somewhere where laziness or shoddy work was

tolerated you know how frustration and demoralization this can be. But it plays out in other way as well. For example: A manager who is afraid of conflict may hesitate to make necessary course correction mid-way through a project

3.6 Delegating Without Truly Delegating :

Sometime a manager is so nervous about or invested in project a project that even, though she has technically assigned it to a staffer she doesn't let really go of it , continuing to drive the work herself or even doing some of it herself . This lead to confusion who is actually responsible for the work getting done and diminished ownership.

3.7 Hitting Rather Than Speaking Straight Forward:

Some managers are kind and polite sugarcoating a difficult conversation. But it's not at all kind to let someone miss an important message. When he sugarcoats some points that herd message is missed or present requirement as mere suggestion, staffers end up confused about expectation and the manager ends up frustrated that their suggestion weren't acted upon. Most employees prefer straightforward communication. So they don't need to figure out what they really supposed to hear

Taking Credit for someone else work never be a credit hog this is someone who cannot go along with or present an idea unless it was his own .Collaboration is a beautiful thing. It never hurts to give credit where credit is due well someone will return you the favor someday Not surprisingly majority of people are also annoyed by some coworkers especially those who have many complaints.

Its seems that these coworkers might be better working at home and they would like to, But half of the survey respondent said that didn't think their employers would agree to letting them do that The survey organizer theorize that most of those employees haven't actually make a request to telecommunicate, But they are assuming their bosses wouldn't be open to it then again considering some employees who do work from home admit to watching TV while they are "working"

Perhaps the employers concern would be understandable

4. Conclusion

Suggestion to Overcome the Problem of Retention

4.1 Leaders should maintain institutional integrity .They integrate the need of the individual with those of the group, so that the goal are easily reached.

4.2 Duties and Responsibilities of all the Employees should be especially determined .Standard should be determined for all the employees so that they may fix the target that they have to accomplish

- 4.3 Leaders should make the path of their workers easy .If any problem faced by workers it should be overcome with providing necessary resources to perform their task.
- 4.4 There should be a clear provision of reward and punishment for the employees .These provision should be clear to all the employees
- 4.5 Disciplinary action should be based upon the enquiry and investigation of all the relevant facts .Therefore it is necessary that all a relevant fact should collected and deeply analyzed before taking any disciplinary action.
- 4.6 There should be well defined code of discipline in the enterprise .Rules, Regulations, Systems and Procedures of the enterprise should be clearly defined and communicated to all the employees

References

1. Ganesan R.Santhanakrishnan, “Non-Performing Assets: A Study of State Bank of India” *Asia Pacific Journal of Re-search*, Volume: I, Issue: X, October 2013.
2. D. Jayakoddi and Dr. P. Rengarajan, “A Study on Non- performing Assets of selected public and private sector banks in India”, *Intercontinental Journal of Finance Research Review* ISSN: 2321-0354 - Online ISSN: 2347-1654 - Print – Impact of Factor: 1.552 VOLUME 4, ISSUE 9, September 2016.
3. Vaibhavi Shah and Sunil Sharma, “A Comparative Study of NPA in ICICI Bank and HDFC Bank”, *Avinava national Monthly Referred Journal of Research in Commerce and Management*. Vol.5, Issue 2, Feb. 2016.
4. Dr. Biswanath Sukul, “Non-Performing Assets (NPAs): A Comparative Analysis of Selected Private Sector Banks”, *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science Invention* ISSN (Online): 2319 – 7722, ISSN (Print):2319–7714, www.ijhssi.org || Volume 6 Issue 1||January. 2017 || PP.47-53.
5. A. Barajas (et al, 2000), R. Steiner and N. Salazar (1999), *Interest Spread in Banking in Columbia, 1974-96*, IMF Paper.
6. Banknet India, Reserve Bank of India. Reserve Bank Guidelines on purchase/ sale of Non-Performing Financial Assets
7. Bama B (2002)” NPL Securitization in China- Anatomy of the deal” Structural Product Group, ICICI Research Ban-galore.